

EFFECT OF PRODUCTION METHOD ON THE PROPERTIES OF PVA/Ag–Cu COMPOSITES

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This thesis presents comparative data on the structural, thermal, and mechanical characteristics, the work of adhesion as well as the anti-mold activity of composites based on PVA and Ag–Cu structures. A one-stage method for obtaining polymer composites with Ag–Cu using underwater pulsed plasma is considered. Two- and three-stage chemical methods for obtaining Ag–Cu structures with/without using the stabilizer (chitosan and polyvinylpyrrolidone) are also compared. The incorporation of the filler into the polymer matrix is confirmed by XRD patterns and FTIR spectroscopy data. The results of thermal and mechanical tests have shown that the synthesis method and the nature of the stabilizer allow the creation of more platy composites. The introduction of Ag–Cu fillers increases the resistance to UV radiation and changes the work of adhesion. The method of production, the concentration of the filler, and the nature of the stabilizer affect the anti-mold activity of the composites. Analysis of obtained results, PVA/Ag–Cu composites can be considered promising food packaging materials.

Within the scope of this study, the results of the anti-mold activity studies can be explained as follows. In the case of sample 7, the gas permeability increases due to the cross-linking of the polymer matrix and stabilizer (PVP). For samples 2–4, the reason may be favorable plasma treatment conditions for the accumulation of hydrogen peroxide in the polymer matrix, which is an antibacterial and anti-mold agent.

Figure 1. Photos of uncoated (blank) and coated by polymer films with Ag–Cu structures (1–7) and without (8) wheat bread pieces after 2 weeks

Photos of uncoated (blank) and coated by polymer films with Ag–Cu structures (1–7) and without (8) wheat bread pieces after 2 weeks

The use of chitosan as a stabilizer of Ag–Cu particles harms the properties of the Ag–Cu/PVA composite. Thus, the use of underwater pulsed plasma and a two-stage chemical method for the synthesis of Ag–Cu structures (using PVP as a stabilizer) are the best methods for obtaining the materials for packing and storing seeds.